

A preparation of hydroalcoholic extract of *Pongamia pinnata* leaves inhibits the apoptosis of cortical neurons in pre/post-stroke rat *via* regulating the expression of BAX/Bcl-2

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Abstract:

Cerebral ischemia/Stroke is a serious condition with second leading mortality and disability. Despite the established standard treatments available, the variability and time consumption are vastly considered as a concern over suitable Stroke management. The aim of the current study is to determine the effect of hydroalcoholic extract of *Pongamia (P) pinnata* on ischemia-induced rat brain. A total of 18 male Wistar rats were investigated and divided into six groups (G1-G6). G4 and G6 group animals were administered with 400 mg of 70% ethanolic extract of *P. pinnata* leaf which was neuroprotective and neuro restorative

groups respectively. The neuroprotective animals(G4) were compared with the G1(positive control), G2(sham control) and G3(Negative control). Neurorestorative group animals(G6) were compared with G1(positive control) and G5(negative control). Ischemia/Reperfusion was incorporated by Bilateral Common Carotid Artery Occlusion (BACCAO) for 60 minutes followed by reperfusion for 24 hours for the neuroprotective group and 21 days for the neurorestorative groups respectively. The Real Time PCR (RT-PCR) assay was performed to study the expression of Bcl-2-associated X-protein (BAX) protein for the neuroprotective and neurorestorative effects of *P. pinnata* leaf extract. The *P. pinnata* leaf extract could significantly decrease cortical neuronal apoptosis and the RT-PCR results showed that BAX protein significantly. The study warrants that the 70% ethanolic leaf extract of *P. pinnata* has neuroprotective and neurorestorative potential in ischemic injury by increasing vascularity and reducing cell death. The results obtained promote a reliable alternative source to deal with Ischemic Stroke conditions.

Introduction

Ischemic stroke is a condition that has been a challenge to address with current mode of treatments. The mortality and disability rates of ischemic stroke have become a major concern worldwide (Campbell BCV et al., 2020). Determination of an effective cure is under focus with the presently available technological improvements. However, a challenge occurs with the pathophysiological condition of cerebral ischemia / reperfusion injury. The condition includes excitotoxicity, oxidative stress, inflammation, and apoptosis in the ischemic penumbra. The current mode of treatments is focused toward antiapoptotic condition or anti-inflammatory conditions or with antioxidizing agents. Few other treatments act as calcium channel blockers and free radical scavengers (Hicken bottom SL et al., 2008).

Cerebral ischemia studies in rats and gerbils have revealed dysregulation of Bcl-2 family proteins that exacerbates ischemic neuronal injury. The interaction between Bcl-2 family members (such as Bcl-2 and Bcl-xl) suppress apoptosis. BAX protein plays a key role in determining cells survival or apoptosis (J Kang JB et al 2023) and is thus necessary for efficient activation of proapoptotic mitochondrial signaling in infected/inflammatory neurons (Kang JB et all 2023).

We explored various herbal medicines available over the world and identified the plant *Pongamia pinnata* being used for various complications (Singh A et al., 2021). *Pongamia (P.) pinnata*, is commonly referred to as the Indian beech tree and known for pongamia oil or karanja. Numerous herbal benefits were known from it that includes antioxidant properties, anti-lipid, anti-inflammatory, antidiarrheal, anti-hyperglycemic, antinociceptive, and various other properties. The phytochemical components of the plant include furano flavonoids, chalcones, alkaloids, carbohydrates, phytosterols, saponins, tannins, and

flavonoids. Furano flavonoids and chalcones are known to exert a neuroprotective activity in various neurodegenerative diseases, such as Parkinson's disease (Al Muqarrabun LMet al 2014).

P. pinnata has proven to possess notable advantages over standard treatment options in regulating multisite and multitarget diseases. The biological activity of *P. pinnata* is capable of promoting neuroprotection such as inhibiting excitotoxicity, apoptosis, inflammation, oxidative stress, and autophagy. In addition, *P. pinnata* could promote angiogenesis, neurogenesis, and axonal sprouting, proving its neurorestorative nature (Swamy AH el al 2013).

Enormous reports of Neuroprotective effects (Swamy AH el al 2013, Knez Hrnčič M et al 2020), using Herbal compounds are vastly available. The present study has pioneered to evaluate the neuroprotective as well as the neurorestorative potential of *P. pinnata* on stroke-induced rat models with the help of the molecular-level analysis.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Chemicals

All chemicals used in this study are analytical and required reference standards for comparison. Preparation of *P. pinnata* extract from leaves was performed by standard methodologies (Knez Hrnčič M et al 2020).

The plant material was derived from mature green leaves of *P. pinnata*. It was collected from Bangalore Medical College and Research Institute Campus. The plant was identified and authenticated at the Herbarium of the Vishveswarapura College of Science. The voucher number of the specimen is B-00010.

The *P. pinnata* leaves are collected and dried under shade. The dried leaves are powdered and packed into a Soxhlet apparatus for an extraction. The extraction was carried out using 70% ethanol. The solvent was

evaporated under room temperature. The ethanolic extract of *P. pinnata* leaves showed presence of flavonoids, flavones, chalcones, terpenes, glycosides, sterols, and tannins. (Degani E et al 2022).

Ethical Clearance

After receiving approval from the Institutional Animal Ethical Committee at Saveetha Dental College, Chennai, India (BRULAC/SDCH/SIMATS/IAEC/08-2022/138), the experiment was carried out. Rat models were subjected to induced stroke (BCCAO method).

Experimental Animals

Wister male rats were used with an age about 10–12 weeks and a weight of 280–320 grams. Rats were fed a commercial rat pellet diet provided by Mass Biotech, Chennai, and were provided with water ad libitum. They were kept at a natural light-and-dark cycle under a temperature of 20–25°C and a humidity of 50 to 60%. Rats were divided into 6 groups. They are G1 (positive control), G2(sham control), G3 (negative control) for neuroprotective group, G4 neuroprotective treated group (treated with 400 mg *P. pinnata*), G5(negative control) for neurorestorative group and G6 neurorestorative treated group (treated with 400 mg *P. pinnata*). The effect of the *P.pinnata* was examined by using RT-PCR to study the expression of BAX protein. It was used to understand the changes that occurred in the brain infarct. The mRNA levels of BAX proteins are analyzed by RT-PCR to see the neuroprotective and neurorestorative effect of *P. pinnata* leaf extract.

BCCAO Model

The stroke induction was done by bilateral common carotid artery occlusion (BCCAO) model (Figure 1). Rats were anesthetized by injection of 0.3 ml of ketamine and xylazine, followed by the crown of the head

shaved and cleaned with 70% alcohol and continuously monitored for spontaneous breathing. The skin incision was done on the ventral aspect of the neck, Both the carotid arteries were visualized and occluded by ligating. It was left for 60 minutes. Under aseptic conditions, the incision was sutured, and the animals were placed in a dry cage separately with the assistance of a heat pad. Temperature was monitored periodically. Neurological examination was done according to Bederson *et al.* (Bederson JB et al 1986).

(Figure-1)

Figure 1. shows the model of Induced BCCAO

In the neuroprotective (G1-G4) and neurorestorative groups(G5-G6), the rats were orally administered with *P. pinnata* leaf 70% ethanolic extract 400 mg/kg for 21 days to group G4 (neuroprotective) and G6 (neurorestorative).

In the neuroprotective group, the rats were euthanized within 24 hours of stroke induction, whereas in the neurorestorative group, the rats were euthanized at day 21 after stroke induction, and the tissue sections of

brain were taken for molecular analysis. The mRNA levels of candidate genes were also analyzed *via* RT-PCR analysis.

Distribution of Groups

The experimental protocol, the study was set up with relevant groups of animals as follows: each group was $n = 3$ (Table 1). The G1 rat models were positive control rat models, where the molecular data of normal rat models was sought. G2 rat models were sham controls for the neuroprotective group, where the surgery was done without proceeding with occlusion. G3 rat models are a negative control for the neuroprotective group, which are subjected to the BCCAO method but not treated with the drug to cause an infarction, and the changes that take place during an ischemic stroke sequence were observed. G4 rat models are the experimental group for the neuroprotective group, which have been subjected to the BCCAO technique, and then ethanolic *P. pinnata* leaf extract was orally administered at a dosage of 400 mg/kg. G5 rat models are negative control for the neurorestorative group, where they were subjected to the BCCAO technique and fed with NS and food for 21 days without any drug. G6 rat models are the experimental neurorestorative group, which have been subjected to the BCCAO technique, and then ethanolic *P. pinnata* leaf extract was orally administered at a dosage of 400 mg/kg.

As stated earlier, the rats are sacrificed at the 21st day of trial, and histological analysis of brain tissues and molecular level analysis of the neurotrophic factors are reviewed.

Table 1, Distribution of Groups

Groups	Details	No. of Animals
G1	Positive control (normal)	4
G2	Sham control for neuroprotective group	4
G3	Negative control for neuroprotective group	4
G4	Experimental neuroprotective group treated with <i>P. pinnata</i> (400 mg/kg)	4
G5	Negative control for neurorestorative group	4
G6	Experimental neurorestorative group treated with <i>P. pinnata</i> 400 mg/kg)	4
	Total number of animals	24

Real-Time PCR Analysis

Traditionally, RT-PCR involves two steps: the RT reaction and PCR amplification. CFX96 Touch Real Time PCR Detection system was used for this analysis. Genes forward primer and reverse primer are as follows:

- Forward primer—TGAAGACAGGGGCCTTTTGG
- Reverse primer—AATTCGCCGGAGACACTCG

Primer designing was the initial step and was done by synthesizing the primers of the target gene. The next step was that of RNA extraction. The brain sections were used to extract the total RNA present in the given model, and this was carried out using the standard protocol with Trizol, which was then dissolved using Diethylpyrocarbonate-treated deionized water and quantified with a spectrophotometer. Enrichment was

done for the RNAs with polyadenylated tails. The next step was, the real-time PCR, wherein the targets were amplified and then set for quantification of gene expression to obtain the fold changes of the targets. Finally, the result analysis was performed to depict the comparative levels of mRNA expression in treated groups and the effect of in animal models (Mo Y el al.,2012, Hua R el al 2018, Wong ML el al., 2005).

Statistical Analysis

The method used was one-way ANOVA (a multiple variance test). For probability criteria, values less than 0.005 were considered significant ($P < 0.005$).

Results

BAX Expression in Neuroprotective Group (G1-G4)

In neuroprotective models that were orally treated with *P. pinnata* leaf extract before induction of stroke for 21 days, followed by euthanized, and levels of BAX were determined (Figure 2).

Figure 2, Graphical representations of real-time PCR analytic results—levels of BAX for neuroprotective group

The levels of BAX increased in the negative control group (G3) compared with the normal group (G1) and experimental group (G4), and it was treated with a 400 mg dosage of the *P. pinnata* leaf extract. The mRNA level is almost the same in the normal control group (G1) and sham control (G2) group.

BAX Expression in Neurorestorative Group (G1, G5, G6)

In the results obtained here, initially poststroke, the levels of BAX were increased, facilitating the mechanism of neuronal injury and brain damage. The BAX levels were compared within the testing groups after 21 days of treatment with *P. pinnata* leaf extract. It was clear that in the positive control models (G1), the BAX expression levels were significantly decreased compared to the negative control models (G5). The level of BAX protein is drastically reduced in the treated group (G6) and almost equal to that of G1. G6 animals had significant neuronal cell survival and recovery of the brain (Figure 3).

Figure 3, Graphical representations of real-time PCR analytic results—BAX levels for neurorestorative group

Discussion

This is a pioneering study to investigate the neurorestorative effect in addition to the neuroprotective effect of Ischemic Stroke after the administration of an herbal extract. Antiplatelet therapy using aspirin and clopidogrel being most commonly used is one of the currently practiced therapeutic options for preventing the Ischemic stroke recurrence (Lee HG et al.,2023). Treatment of stroke in early stages is of prime significance to obtain recovery and prevent the recurrence of stroke (Patil S et al., 2022).

Understanding the pathophysiology of stroke has considerable improvements with primary focus on restoration of blood flow to the brain and then attempting to treat the stroke-induced neurological damage (Kuriakose D et al, 2020). After the Ischemic Stroke incidence, some neurons survive in the ischemic penumbra around the damaged brain tissues, and it requires the damaged neurons to be restored for blood perfusion in the ischemic penumbra. Nevertheless, blood flow reperfusion usually aggravates the ischemic condition and causes further serious impact on reperfusion of injuries in the brain tissue that happens to be a factor for higher mortality and disability rate of Ischemic Stroke (Zhu Z et al., 2021).

Agents that provide neuroprotective support, generally protects the ischemic penumbra, that impacts in improving the prognosis of patients. Neuroprotective property is thus vital in treating Ischemic Stroke. Predominant research is focusing on identifying neuroprotective drugs that is effective against Ischemic Stroke (Kuriakose D et al, 2020). However, there is inadequate focus on the neurorestorative therapies that restore improvements in quality of life (Azad TD et al.,2016). Drugs with both the neuroprotective and neurorestorative effect are major intervention approaches for Ischemic stroke as the factors associated with acute and ischemic brain injury includes excitotoxicity, inflammation, angiogenesis, and neurogenesis. In addition, the interactions with blood-brain barrier permeability, increased structural damage in the

neurovascular unit along with the hemorrhagic transition happens during ischemic stroke (Zhu T et al., 2012).

A study by Li et al., has proposed *Pongamia pinnata* to possess potential therapeutic agents for neurodegenerative diseases with their known anti-inflammatory activities (Li J, Jiang Z et al., 2015). Apart from its significant phytochemical compounds, historical applications to various complications are well established and validated to provide therapeutic remedy (Al Muqarrabun LM et al., 2013). In the present study, *Pongamia pinnata* was used to treat Ischemic Stroke wistar rat models, and the changes of the clinical condition by evaluating the Bcl-2-associate X protein (BAX) protein expressions was used to assess the prognosis post various dosages. BAX is protein that executes mitochondria regulated cell death *via* its lethal activity by permeabilizing the outer membrane of Mitochondria. Physiological function of BAX includes tissue homeostatis, BAX dysregulation leading to cell death. Approaches to cover targeted therapeutic agents with BAX is of primary requirement (Spitz AZ, Gavathiotis E et al., 2022).

Significance of Candidate Targets Analyzed by Real-Time PCR Analysis

Expression of BAX protein is usually seen to be in elevated condition in neurological diseases and neuronal damage (Gillardon F et al., 1996). Immune reactivity for BAX protein is often increased in injured neurons and ischemic experimental models after a traumatic brain injury sequence (Raghupathi R et al., 2003, Chen J et al., 1996). BAX remains unchanged in its level when the neurons survive without being affected (Chen DF et al., 1997).

On correlating with the observed findings, it was found that the potential increase in BAX expression gave an undesirable outcome by facilitating Apoptosis and hence neuronal cell death. The increase in BAX

expression is thus attributed to the fact that BAX plays a vital role in apoptosis by increasing the cellular permeability to cytochrome c, causing mitochondrial dysfunction, and facilitating the mechanisms that cause cell death (Wu C et al., 2003). BAX expression has been identified in immunoreactivity and the areas of infarction and absent in nonischemic areas. Hence, it would be logical to consider the downregulation of BAX expression after the administration of *P. pinnata* leaf extract as a positive indicator of poststroke recovery (Schäbitz WR et al., 2000).

Plant Extracts and *P.pinnata* application

In the study done by Kang et al., 271 of the 963 genes were related with apoptosis as well as immune reaction, inflammatory response, angiogenesis, and vasculogenesis. Most significantly, the anti-activity of Ginkgol Biloba extract (GBE) in ischemic cardio-cerebrovascular diseases has long been accounted for, and its system of activity is firmly connected with the statement of BAX, Bcl-2, and Caspase-3 in hippocampal neurons (Kang X et al., 2007).

Numerous research studies have utilized different parts of *P. pinnata* plant material [6]. Thakur et al. (1989) described the medicinal impacts of ethanolic extract of *P. pinnata* roots (Wen R et al., 2019). Swamy et al., (2013) explored the impact of *P. pinnata* stem bark on monosodium glutamate stroke-actuated rodents, and the outcomes were satisfactory (Swamy AH et al 2013).

These data support the findings wherein *P. pinnata* flower extract was shown to exert a protective effect in cisplatin- and gentamycin-induced renal injury, owing to the antioxidative property of the plant. The observed beneficial effect may be attributed to the presence of flavonoids, which exhibit antioxidant properties (Al Muqarrabun L Met al 2014). Anup et al. (2011) discovered that petroleum ether extract of

stem bark *P. pinnata* was found to have great anticonvulsant properties on laboratory rats (Bhandirge SK et al.,2015). *P. pinnata* significantly has good neuroprotective and neurorestorative effects on stroke-induced rat brain.

The current study has used the leaf extract of *P. pinnata* that was able to protect and reverse ischemia-reperfusion injury in neuroprotective and neurorestorative groups, respectively, brought about by ischemic stroke. The outcomes affirmed that the values of BAX protein were increased in stroke-induced rats, which decreased significantly after *P. pinnata* organization in the neuroprotective and neurorestorative groups.

Conclusion

The results showed a neuroprotective and neurorestorative *P. pinnata* leaf extract effect on cerebral ischemia. *P. pinnata* inhibits/ reduces neuronal apoptosis by regulating BAX/Bcl-2. The study has demonstrated that, the pattern of the BAX protein expression is disrupted in motor cortex area after Bccao procedure. Therefore, *P. pinnata* leaf extract may be a promising treatment strategy to reduce neuronal damage and improve the prognosis of stroke victims.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors of this manuscript declare that there are no financial interests associated with this publication and disclose no conflicts of interest exist.

Author's Contributions

Suganitha B: Conceptualization, methodology, study preparation and conducting, original draft preparation, Reviewing and editing, Statistics and data curation

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